

**EDUCATORS' READINESS FOR ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE INTEGRATION
INTO SOCIAL STUDIES: A MULTI - LEVEL STUDY
IN TARABA STATE, NIGERIA**

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DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17246932>

Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI), as a new technology, has played a significant role in every sphere of human endeavour. In education, it has introduced new opportunities for teaching and learning across disciplines, reshaping methods, techniques, and approaches to knowledge acquisition. However, Nigerian Social Studies education has yet to fully embrace its potential. This study examines the levels of AI awareness, perceived benefits, and preparedness among Social Studies educators in Taraba State, Nigeria, and explores how teaching level, educational qualification, gender, and teaching experience influence these factors. A survey of 528 Social Studies educators was conducted using a validated questionnaire. Data were analysed using Welch's ANOVA, Games-Howell tests, and bootstrapped two-way ANOVA. Results showed that teaching level significantly influenced AI awareness, with tertiary educators reporting the highest awareness ($p < .001$, $\eta^2 = .08$). Teaching experience was a decisive factor: early- and mid-career educators (1–10 years) perceived greater benefits and preparedness than those with 11 years or more ($p < .001$, $\eta^2 = .07$). Educational qualification and gender had no significant effect. The study concludes that institutional level and teaching experience, rather than qualification or gender, influence AI readiness. It recommends targeted professional development for experienced teachers, urgent curriculum reforms, equitable digital infrastructure, and supportive policy interventions to ensure inclusive AI integration in Social Studies education.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Educators, Integration, Social Studies, Readiness

Introduction

Education systems worldwide, and in Nigeria in particular, are undergoing rapid transformation driven by digital innovation and the growing influence of Artificial Intelligence (AI). In teaching and learning, Artificial Intelligence is reshaping curriculum design, learner engagement, and assessment, prompting educators and policymakers to rethink pedagogy. Luckin (2017) reveals AI's potential in developing adaptive and personalised assessment systems, showing how technology can support teachers in tracking learner progress more effectively. Similarly, Holmes, Bialik, and Fadel (2019) emphasise AI's broader role in pedagogy and fostering competencies such as critical thinking and problem-solving. These developments are changing the professional expectations of teachers compelling educators to embrace digital competence as a professional necessity.

In Nigeria, however, the integration of AI into classroom practice remains at a formative stage. Social Studies, a discipline introduced in the 1970s to foster civic responsibility, social cohesion, and national consciousness (Ogundare, 2003; Mezieobi, Fubara, & Mezieobi, 2008), has largely retained its traditional, teacher-centred orientation. Scholars have long criticised the curriculum for failing to reflect the demands of contemporary digital society, especially in areas such as media literacy, data use, and digital citizenship (Mkpa, 1987; Mezieobi & Osakwe, 2013). This disconnect limits the subject's capacity to prepare learners for participatory citizenship in a digitally mediated world.

Previous research has shown that technology integration is not only determined by access to tools but also by teacher beliefs, digital competence, and contextual realities (Ertmer, 2005; OECD, 2020). In Nigeria, infrastructural deficits, outdated teacher training curricula, and limited professional development opportunities compound the challenge (Ajiboye & Olatundun, 2010; Sofadekan, 2012). Supporting this view, Oyewole and Nathan (2025) found that technological self-efficacy and access to digital resources significantly predict AI usability among Social Sciences lecturers in Nigerian colleges of education. While global studies have linked teacher beliefs, competence, and context to technology readiness, no study has examined these dynamics within Nigerian Social Studies educators across multiple teaching levels. This study addresses that gap.

Research Objectives

This study was guided by the following objectives and hypotheses:

- i. To examine the relationship between Social Studies educators' teaching level and their awareness of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Taraba State.
- ii. To investigate the interaction between educational qualification and teaching experience in predicting perceived benefits of AI integration.
- iii. To assess the interaction between gender and teaching experience in predicting preparedness for AI adoption.

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no statistically significant relationship between Social Studies educators' teaching level and their AI awareness.

H₀₂: There is no significant interaction between educational qualification and teaching experience in predicting perceived benefits of AI integration.

H₀₃: There is no significant interaction between gender and teaching experience in predicting preparedness for AI adoption.

Methodology

A descriptive survey design was employed, targeting Social Studies educators in primary, secondary, and tertiary institutions. A snowball sampling method was used due to the dispersed

nature of educators across rural and urban schools, making probability sampling impractical. Initial contacts were made through the Taraba State chapter of the Social Studies Association of Nigeria (SOSAN), whose members referred eligible colleagues within their networks. A total of 528 valid responses were obtained. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire consisting of 28 core items rated on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree). The instrument underwent expert review to establish content validity. Internal consistency reliability was confirmed with a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.82, indicating strong reliability. However, no construct validity test was conducted; this remains a limitation of the study. For inferential analysis, Welch's ANOVA was applied to test for significant differences across teaching levels, as the assumption of homogeneity of variance was violated. Games-Howell post hoc tests were then used for pairwise comparisons. In addition, bootstrapped two-way ANOVA procedures (1,000 samples) were employed to examine the interaction effects of teaching experience with qualification (on perceived benefits) and gender (on preparedness).

Ethical considerations were observed throughout the study. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all respondents. Anonymity and confidentiality were assured by excluding personal identifiers from the dataset. The study received ethical clearance from the College of Education, Zing, Research Ethics Committee, ensuring compliance with institutional standards for human subjects research.

Results

Hypothesis one: There is no statistically significant relationship between Social Studies educators' teaching level and their AI awareness in Taraba State.

Table 1: Awareness by Teaching Level (Welch's ANOVA + Games-Howell)

Teaching Level	N	Mean	SD	p-value
Primary	245	2.79	0.71	.003
Secondary	211	3.02	0.78	.000
Tertiary	72	3.59	0.71	–

Analysis of Table 1 shows Welch's ANOVA and Games-Howell post hoc comparisons on the differences in AI awareness among Social Studies educators across educational levels in Taraba State. The findings shows that AI awareness differed significantly across teaching levels. Tertiary educators reported the highest awareness ($M = 3.59$, $SD = 0.71$), followed by secondary ($M = 3.02$, $SD = 0.78$) and primary educators ($M = 2.79$, $SD = 0.71$). Pairwise comparisons showed significant differences between tertiary and both secondary (-0.56 , $p < .001$) and primary educators (-0.80 , $p < .001$), as well as a smaller but significant difference between secondary and primary educators (-0.23 , $p = .003$). Based on the results, the null hypothesis (H_{01}) was rejected indicating that teaching level significantly influenced AI awareness. The findings show that higher institutional affiliation corresponds to greater exposure to or engagement with AI technologies. Tertiary educators' elevated awareness may be linked to their access to research, digital resources, and professional development, whereas primary educators may face structural and training-related barriers that limit their familiarity with AI.

Hypothesis two: There is no significant interaction between educational qualification and teaching experience in predicting perceived benefits of AI integration among Social Studies educators in Taraba State.

Table 2: Perceived AI Benefits by Qualification and Teaching Experience (Two-Way ANOVA)

Qualification	1–5 yrs (M, SD)	6–10 yrs (M, SD)	11+ yrs (M, SD)	p-value
NCE	3.63 (0.04)	3.52 (0.07)	2.03 (0.32)	
B.Ed/B.Sc(Ed)	3.63 (0.04)	3.65 (0.04)	2.38 (0.15)	
M.Ed/M.Sc(Ed)	3.48 (0.17)	3.49 (0.12)	2.38 (0.24)	
PhD	4.00*	3.60*	2.17*	
Main Effect:Experience				< .001***
Main Effect:Qualification				.227
Interaction (Qual × Exp.)				.623

Table 2 shows the results for perceived benefits of AI integration by qualification and teaching experience. Educators with 1–5 years of experience reported the highest perceived benefits across qualifications (M = 3.48–3.63, SD ≈ 0.04–0.17), followed by those with 6–10 years (M = 3.49–3.65, SD ≈ 0.04–0.12). By contrast, educators with 11 or more years of experience reported much lower benefits (M = 2.03–2.38, SD ≈ 0.15–0.32). Results for PhD holders (M = 2.17–4.00). The findings show that teaching experience had a significant effect (p < .001***), while qualification and the interaction between qualification and experience were not significant (p = .227 and .623). The null hypothesis was accepted, meaning qualification did not interact with experience. However, the main effect of experience was decisive: early- and mid-career educators viewed AI more positively than those with longer service.

Hypothesis three: There is no significant interaction between gender and teaching experience in predicting preparedness for AI adoption among Social Studies educators in Taraba State.

Table 3: Bootstrapped Two-Way ANOVA Summary and Descriptive Statistics for Educators’ Preparedness for AI Adoption by Gender and Teaching Experience (N = 528)

A. Bootstrapped Descriptive Statistics

Teaching Experience	Gender	N	Mean Preparedness	Std. Deviation	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper
1–5 years	Male	151	3.434	0.475	3.363	3.513
	Female	143	3.446	0.433	3.373	3.518
6–10 years	Male	100	3.463	0.452	3.379	3.549
	Female	86	3.366	0.454	3.274	3.471
11+ years	Male	29	3.098	0.832	2.756	3.379
	Female	19	3.140	0.729	2.794	3.451
Total		528	3.403	0.501	3.359	3.446

B. Bootstrapped Two-Way ANOVA Results

Source	df	F	Sig.	Partial η^2
Teaching Experience	2	8.475	.000	.031
Gender	1	0.059	.809	.000
Teaching Experience \times Gender	2	0.812	.444	.003
Error	522			

The analysis in Table 3 above shows the results of a bootstrapped two-way ANOVA assessing the influence of gender and teaching experience on educators' preparedness for AI adoption. The analysis included 528 Social Studies educators categorised by three levels of teaching experience (1–5 years, 6–10 years, and 11 years and above) and by gender (male and female). Bootstrapped two-way ANOVA results showed a significant main effect of teaching experience on preparedness ($F(2, 522) = 8.475, p < .001, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .031$). Educators with more than 11 years of teaching reported the lowest preparedness. Gender showed no significant effect ($p = .809$), and the interaction between gender and experience was also not significant ($p = .444$). The null hypothesis was accepted for gender and interaction effects, but rejected for teaching experience. Thus, preparedness for AI adoption decreases with experience, regardless of gender.

Discussion of Findings

This study reveals AI awareness differed significantly across educational levels in Taraba State. Tertiary educators reported higher levels of AI awareness than their secondary and primary counterparts. This outcome is consistent with Luckin (2017) and Holmes, Bialik, and Fadel (2019), who observed that exposure to research, global pedagogical trends, and access to professional development enhances teachers' familiarity with emerging technologies. In contrast, primary and secondary educators in Nigeria appear constrained by inadequate infrastructure and limited training opportunities, which reinforces the digital divide within the education sector (Ajiboye & Olatundun, 2010).

Teaching experience significantly influenced perceived benefits of AI integration. Early- and mid-career educators (1–10 years) reported greater perceived benefits, whereas educators with more than 11 years of experience indicated much lower benefits. This finding resonates with OECD (2020), which states that younger educators are typically more digitally literate and adaptive to innovations. Conversely, longer-serving educators may rely on established pedagogical routines and lack access to sustained retraining, which limits their perception of AI's educational value. This pattern reflects what Ertmer (2005) described as the role of teacher beliefs and contextual realities in shaping technology integration.

Preparedness for AI adoption declined with experience, while gender had no significant effect. This finding indicates that years of teaching experience negatively influenced educators' readiness to adopt AI. Longer-serving educators reported lower preparedness compared to early- and mid-career teachers. This supports Ertmer's (2005) argument that teacher beliefs and entrenched pedagogical practices can act as barriers to technology integration. Similarly, OECD (2020) emphasized that digital competence and openness to innovation are often higher among younger teachers, who may be more adaptable to technological change. By contrast, gender did not significantly affect preparedness, which is consistent with Sofadekan (2012), who found that male and female educators demonstrate comparable technological competence when given similar access and training.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined the readiness of Social Studies educators across primary, secondary, and tertiary institutions in Taraba State for integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) into teaching. The findings reveal that AI readiness among Nigerian Social Studies educators is influenced more by teaching level and teaching experience than by qualification or gender. Therefore, the following recommendations were made:

1. Ministries of Education and teacher training institutions should design specialised AI-focused professional development programs for experienced educators, especially at primary and secondary levels, to close preparedness gaps.
2. Teacher education curricula should be urgently updated at all levels (especially postgraduate) to integrate practical, AI-driven pedagogical applications for Social Studies
3. Government and stakeholders must ensure equitable provision of digital infrastructure, internet access, and AI tools across schools in rural and urban areas.

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